

CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ANALYTICAL THINKING IN FUTURE PEDAGOGUES

Mamayusupov Jamshid Shoyunus ugli

Researcher of Fergana Polytechnic Institute

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10648817>

Abstract: The article examines the concept of analytical thinking, its content and structure. The conditions for the development of analytical thinking are analyzed.

Key words: analytical thinking, structural structure, logical, critical and analytical thinking, improvement, pedagogue.

Introduction

Today, in order to ensure future pedagogues have their place in the labor market, it is necessary to develop the skills of social experience in them. That is why there is a need to reform the educational process and create new pedagogical methods of training highly analytical thinking personnel who can show their personality, abandoning the old-fashioned teaching and examination system. In this process, future pedagogues need to develop logical analytical skills, information, reality, problem analysis and synthesis, induction and deduction thinking. In this regard, it should be noted that the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated October 8, 2019 "On approval of the concept of the development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" is of great practical, theoretical and historical importance. reaches [1].

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Analytical thinking has been researched by many scientists in various disciplines, especially philosophy, psychology and pedagogy, and this process continues today. Among them, D. Sharipova, O. Musurmonova, M. Kuronov, U. Mahkamov, R. Safarova, Sh. Mardonov, D. Roziyeva, N. Egamberdiyeva, Sh. Shodmonova, Sh. Sharipov, O. Jamoldinova, V. Slastenin, I. Isayev, Y. Shiyanov, Z. T. Soliyeva's scientific research studies have explored the philosophical, psychological and pedagogical aspects of analytical thinking, existing problems and the factors to overcome them.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. In the conditions of the increasing demand for modern pedagogues and the growing need for their professional knowledge and skills, future pedagogues should have high professional training, loyalty to their profession, adaptability to changing social life, regular training in an independent state. The main task is to improve one's knowledge, to constantly

give suggestions and recommendations, to independently analyze one's activities. It should be noted that the quality of higher education is closely related to the training of highly qualified specialists [2].

The specific pedagogical features of developing analytical thinking in future pedagogues are as follows:

- a comprehensive approach to the education of future pedagogues, formation of socio-philosophical knowledge in them along with specialized subjects, organization of the educational process based on the latest pedagogical technologies;
- to create a scientific environment that develops the analytical thinking of future pedagogues as a deep and critical thinker, who can stand in a creative, objective position;
- in the pedagogical process, introducing an innovative methodology for developing logical thinking and analytical thinking, which is very useful in the professional activity of future pedagogues;
- it is necessary to inculcate in future pedagogues the skills of working with people individually and in a team, adaptability to the times and social environment, to give special knowledge on forming the ability to solve problems on the spot, and to form these characteristics;
- in the training of future pedagogues, it is necessary to develop critical and analytical skills, as well as the skills to make the right decision and get out of various situations;
- developing a methodology for working with practical "cases" in the training of future pedagogues, not limited to theoretical knowledge.

In order to develop analytical thinking, we must first determine what this thinking is. In fact, original analytical thinking must have elements of skepticism. For example, "The skepticism founded by Pyrrhon was of inestimable importance for the development of critical thinking. However, the formation of critical thinking is very important not only for the economist, but also for the daily life of any person. After all, no one can turn a person with a critical thinking into his "puppet", and he makes fewer mistakes in his life than others. But there is also great confusion about what critical thinking is. The worst of these confusions is that a person can't see his own mistakes and shortcomings by focusing this criticism only on the outside. In order to avoid such shortcomings and to prevent the student from becoming a "sophist" (demagogue, sophist) in a negative sense" [4], it is necessary to prepare to identify the main features of critical thinking.

Critical thinking is thinking that is not aimed at finding errors and flaws in the opinion of others, but at analytically studying certain information. Accordingly, critical thinking within the framework of a true, high culture includes the following aspects:

openness to new thoughts and ideas that oppose his own;

to avoid making mistakes in one's thoughts and views, and strive to eliminate them;

striving to distinguish right and wrong among different opinions without bias, i.e. objectively;

not to express a critical opinion on an issue that he could not understand, to admit that he does not understand;

distinguish between justified and unjustified errors in thought, etc. Of course, if a person has a strong interest in knowledge, then the culture of critical thinking is intuitively well formed. However, vices such as arrogance and a tendency to flaunt one's personality, pre-formed in the student's character, are a great obstacle to the formation of the original critical thinking, which is very necessary for the development of analytical thinking.

Analytical thinking is a complex way of thinking, the formation of which goes through various stages, starting from the passive reception of information to independently coming to the solution of certain problems. Critical thinking is strongly developed in students in the true sense. So, in order for us to educate our students as specialists with high analytical thinking, we must first of all create conditions for awakening and developing the ability of critical thinking. In this case, the critical spirit and way of thinking in the pedagogue's lectures serve as the most important and necessary conditions, ground, and basis.

However, critical thinking is not easy and fast, but is a complex theoretical and didactic process that goes through certain stages, so it requires certain methodological preparation from the pedagogue. The formation of critical thinking in the pedagogical process mainly consists of the following stages:

creating the conditions for critical thinking.

to invite critical thinking.

critical understanding of the material.

Today's education aims to develop the following in future personnel by emphasizing analytical thinking:

Leadership of the mind is the ability to come up with not one, but several solutions to problems that most people don't have time to think about in a given time frame, and to justify the unique pros and cons of each of them.

The flexibility of thinking is the realization that the template directions and principles accepted in society and traditionally existing, which are actually thought to be correct, are no longer able to respond to modern development, perceive new directions and measures, and think about them. to be able to receive and form, to be able to rebuild one's activity and to be able to mobilize oneself in new directions of problem solving.

Prognosis, and the ability to predict, is the thinking of understanding in advance the nature of future changes in the development of one's field, the causes of their origin, and the periods of their occurrence through a mental analysis. For example, the rise and fall of labor productivity, changes in business conditions or the market and the impact of these changes on the industry, the rise and fall of prices, etc.

The types of thinking methods and their origin, essence and specific aspects are analyzed below:

In the development of analytical thinking in future pedagogues, it is also effective to teach the important aspects of thinking styles, the process of formation of certain styles in thinking, and the change of thinking style in intellectual development. In particular, it will be appropriate to study the sophistic way of thinking. Sophistic thinking in many textbooks and manuals is based on the Greek word "sopism", that is, by deliberately using concepts with different meanings, which are desirable but not true, it is argued that it is a way to achieve portable meaning. When this method is used, the content of the thought is expressed figuratively, that is, a situation similar to "My daughter will tell you, my daughter-in-law, you will listen" is taken. Later, this word gradually began to acquire a different meaning: thinkers who made a name for themselves in eloquence and wisdom began to be called sophists. In later times, the term sophist was also applied to a person who skillfully uses words to confuse people and confuse them. Until now, the concept of "sophists" has been used and understood in the last sense. In the latter sense, the sophists understood that truth can be known by contrasting and juxtaposing words and phrases, revealing their mysterious meaning and significance. In sophistic thinking, the formal connection of the same concepts, words, phrases with others takes first place. It's really nothing more than a meaningless play on words. Sophistic thinking is not interested in words and concepts that have an objective basis [4]. That is why sophistry is wrapped up in the circle of words.

Another way of thinking is metaphysical thinking. Metaphysical thinking mainly thinks based on things, their essence and content. In this sense, the metaphysical

method of thinking differs from sophistic thinking. This method is a way of studying things and events in the metaphysical world that focuses more attention on their relatively unchanged, isolated state over a certain period of time. When this method is used, the main attention is paid to a particular part or state of the forms of manifestation of the world and the processes connected with them. Perfect study of natural objects, striving to reveal their essence in depth is a positive aspect of metaphysical way of thinking. Its main shortcoming is that it does not take into account that things and events in nature are interconnected, that they are constantly changing and developing.

In fact, although the world is in dialectical change and movement, this process does not always happen very quickly. And we are so metaphysically used to things, events and people in the world that it seems as if there is no difference between yesterday and today. In this sense, in many cases in life, we think in a metaphysical way, we react to something in this way. In fact, we rarely think about the fact that they are people and things that have undergone eternal changes. Similarly, our life is a dialectical process that flows from night to tomorrow [4]. This is how we change, but in many cases we don't pay much attention to it.

Another way of thinking is the eclectic way of thinking. Eclectic thinking is a way of thinking that is based on more ambiguous principles, which are important and non-essential, do not take into account the difference between primary and secondary connections, and look at different, often opposing sides of things. Eclectics mechanically connects different aspects and properties of things and events and follows the principle of making more ambiguous conclusions about them "from one side" or "from the other". Inability to distinguish the main decisive aspects in the concrete-historical relationship, real movement, change and development process in the world, in the set of relationships of things and events, is considered to be the main methodological defect of electronic thinking. Logical thinking is also an effective way to develop the analytical thinking of future pedagogues. The method of logical thinking is knowledge formed on the basis of the laws of logic, i.e. logical thinking focuses on the essence, excludes subjective, misinterpretation, and moves from one idea to another on the basis of objective connection, i.e. based on rational thinking. In the process of discussion, logic analyzes the decisive laws of connection in our thoughts, according to them, it forms the rules that we need to base ourselves on in order to create truth. In this regard, correct thinking based on these laws is a necessary condition for creating logical truth. In this sense, learning logical

thinking and strictly following its rules is a necessary factor for the development of human thinking, knowledge and analytical thinking. Knowing it gives an opportunity to achieve clarity in discussion, conclusion and truth in reasoning [3].

The dialectical method is also highly effective in developing analytical thinking in future pedagogues. In the pedagogical process, it is important to teach the common use of thinking styles. In this regard, the role of dialectical thinking is invaluable. One of the important principles of dialectical thinking is objective and scientific analysis of things in the process of their natural movement and development. The main requirements of this method in terms of scientific knowledge are as follows: first, when studying any object or phenomenon, it is necessary to take into account all aspects and connections, as well as its interactions with other objects and phenomena. This is not an abstract requirement, but the things in real reality are not separated from each other, separate, but exist in strong interconnections with each other and require each other [4]. Therefore, the logic of human thinking, which is a reflection of the logic of things, should fully encompass the living and diverse relationship of things and events in the world with the entire external world, and it should be correctly reflected. should be done.

Another feature of dialectical thinking is that it reflects the laws of the development of things and events in the world through the use of compact, mobile, changing concepts in the human mind. It is known that when it comes to the nature of logical categories, there are two conflicting views: metaphysical and dialectical. Metaphysicians interpret categories as immutable, fixed concepts. They do not recognize that the categories can be transferred from one to the other and become their opposite. However, according to development, people themselves create different concepts, ideas, and categories according to their lives. But as these processes change and become others, the categories are not eternal as they are, but by their essence are transitory and historical phenomena.

In the process of development, generations, eras, political systems, social events and events in general happen automatically by themselves and do not disappear without a trace. Perhaps all of them appear as a product of interaction and relations between people, a result of social processes, a consequence of a cause. One era replaces another, one generation after the previous one, one event happens after another. This eternal and ageless continuity, constant connection, connections in the form of non-reversibility of time and sequence of events,

development and progress, diversity and harmony of the universe constitute the basic principles of dialectics.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in today's digital education environment, in the development of professional competence and pedagogical skills of future pedagogues, it is necessary to have an analytical way of thinking and high analytical and cognitive thinking skills. Analytical thinking is important as a characteristic of the future staff's approach to problems based on logical and critical thinking.

References:

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh.M. Mirziyoev "On approval of the concept of development of the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030". <https://uza.uz/oz/documents/zbekiston-respublikasi-oliy-talim-tizimini-2030-yilgacha-riv-09-10-2019>
2. Abrorov I. Higher education system develops based on modern approaches. People's Word, April 26, 2017.
3. Mirgosimova, M. M. (2020) Technology of developing analytical thinking in students. Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University: Vol. 2 : Iss. 4, Article 89.
4. Philosophy encyclopedic dictionary. Tashkent.: National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan. 2004, -B. 26.